

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ASPECTS OF INTELLECTUAL RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN INDUSTRY AREAS

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Abstract

The article explains the theoretical basis of not using intellectual capital in the industrial sector and the importance of its high efficiency. Here, it is fully scientifically justified that the ability to gather knowledge, the ability to learn and knowledge assets, and the skills to manage them have cultural, communication and innovation abilities. The functional qualities of personal intellectual capital and the nature of the relationships between its elements have been determined. At the same time, against the background of the globalization of the world economy, the importance of the need for efficient use of intellectual resources in Azerbaijan and the directions for improving the management of intellectual resources in the economy using the experience of developed countries in this field were given.

Keywords: *human capital, intellect, innovation, science, education, knowledge, model, university, human capital, management.*

INTRODUCTION

In the theory of modern industrial economy, types of human capital, intellectual and organizational resources are distinguished. Sustainable development of the industry is associated with large-scale technological transformation, major changes in the structure of employment.

Intellectual capital is knowledge of such a level and quality that it is capable of creating and applying intellectual products in industrial sectors, providing intellectual services, and using them to create innovative technologies in order to generate income. There are different approaches to understanding intellectual capital among scholars and researchers. For example, E. Brooking equates intellectual capital with four-part intangible assets. This includes people, infrastructure assets, intellectual property, and the primary structural unit is a person's personal intellectual capital [1].

Teams with synergistic intellectual capital and high efficiency of innovative activity are of great importance in the innovative economy. Thus, the basis of increasing the efficiency of the intellectual capital of organizations is the personal intellectual capital of the organization's specialists and universities, which provides the greatest increase in efficiency due to the high quality that has functional and socio-economic aspects. The functional quality of personal intellectual capital is determined by the quality of its elements, accumulated knowledge, intellectual abilities (including skills, intellectual competences, information processing and decision-making models).

Currently, the most important assets of many companies and firms in the innovative economy of developed countries are intellectual resources. According to scientific and practical experts, this sector of the economy makes up a large part of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the economies of those countries, and it is often called the intellectual production sector.

Against the background of the globalization of the world economy, Azerbaijan faces the need for efficient use of human resources, which should lead to the implementation of quality changes based on new knowledge.

The well-known economist Strassman P writes that knowledge is the main source of sustainable competitive advantage. In his monograph on knowledge (human capital) management, he explains that there are 2 different approaches to knowledge management.

First, knowledge management is information management in which information systems are of particular importance.

Second, knowledge management is people management. According to this approach, knowledge management deals with the development of knowledge processes and is related to the development and improvement of employees' competencies to improve the company's performance [2].

Knowledge competence is a complex concept that includes both operational and strategic outcomes of an organization and must be considered at both the individual and organizational levels. Knowledge core competence is the unique knowledge and technology represented by the organization. Therefore, an organization's efficiency and ability to deliver high-quality products and services are key performance-oriented capabilities. These abilities create favorable conditions for the use of organizational core knowledge competencies. Here the competence of knowledge is the most important in terms of its assets.

Knowledge acquisition capabilities include learning ability and knowledge assets, while their management capabilities include cultural, communication, and innovation capabilities. That is, the ability to accumulate knowledge helps to adapt knowledge assets to the competitive environment. The ability to manage knowledge affects the efficiency and profitability of

knowledge assets. These elements of knowledge competence form a relationship, where the level of each of them determines the level of knowledge competence.

The main goals of managing intellectual resources.

Based on the scientific researches of prominent scientists and our centuries of research on this topic, we can conclude that the main tasks of the intellectual resources management process are:

- determining the priorities of scientific and technical development of the organization;
- preparation and use of the knowledge portal;
- development and implementation of the international scientific and technical cooperation program;
- increasing the number of scientific-research and experimental-constructive works;
- regularly updating the knowledge base and analyzing its relevance;
- includes the formation of the intellectual property portfolio and its effective management.

According to the presented concepts, we can define the elements of knowledge powers as follows:

1. Knowledge assets are all knowledge available in the company, including open and hidden. Knowledge elements allow to achieve organizational goals at a strategic level. Knowledge assets are considered intangible resources of the company. Knowledge in an organization is constantly changing.

2. Knowledge learning is a continuous process that creates new knowledge and improves existing knowledge in the organization.

3. Intelligence management is the direct application of knowledge in the enterprise. This competency element reflects the company's ability to use knowledge where and when it is needed. In addition, knowledge management stimulates the development of knowledge assets and knowledge learning. That is, scientific innovation, initiative, creative tendencies can act as internal values of the organization that form the basis of the innovative culture of the company in a certain sense [3,4].

Many scholars refer to the competences resulting from the purposeful use and management of human resources to gain competitive advantage in markets as knowledge management competencies [Figure 1].

Figure 1. Elements of intellectual knowledge

It is clear from Figure 1 that the management of intellectual knowledge is a dynamic organizational phenomenon consisting of interdependent processes, which include the acquisition of knowledge, the transformation of knowledge into a useful form, and the application (or use) of knowledge.

It is clear from our research that Azerbaijan's industrial companies should pay attention to knowledge management skills in order to compete in world markets. In order to increase the competitiveness of the economic sectors of our republic, enterprises must create organizational knowledge and gather experience.

Issues related to strategy, leadership, and culture are critical success factors for a knowledge management program in firms using the system. In addition, technology, structure, and culture are the infrastructural capabilities required for knowledge asset management [5,6].

In today's innovative conditions, the concept of human capital, which includes knowledge and skills, is becoming extremely relevant. The efficiency of production activity, commercial success and profitability of organizations directly depends on the availability, efficient use and further development of human capital. The main goal here is to increase the role of education

and science in improving human capital for sustainable economic growth and competitiveness of the country.

According to most scientists, human capital is the main factor of economic growth:

- knowledge, experience, competence, education;
- acquired qualifications;
- cultural and moral environment;
- creative approach;
- health, ability to work and create innovations, work experience and professional education;
- welfare level;
- rational, physical, intellectual and psychological potential.

From the point of view of the nature of human capital as an economic category using investment and resource approaches, human capital should be understood as a set of personal assets formed through investments that give an economic effect from the use of a person throughout his life.

It is known that the main properties of human capital:

- qualified workforce (employees who are carriers of the necessary knowledge and have the skills, abilities, skills and certain experience to perform highly qualified work);

- a set of knowledge and skills (a knowledge base related to a certain discipline);
- a certain degree of qualification (suitability for preparation for any type of study), practical skills (practical experience);
- the ability to make innovative changes (a person's ability and ability to adapt to various changes in different areas of life);
- value systems (the general value of certain important values in their lives in relation to certain things and events), business culture and philosophy (a certain system of views and values that reveal some features of business as a separate category). human activity), characteristic only for specific organizations.

Thus, human capital is a set of the most important components that reflect the qualitative side of human abilities and skills.

Factors affecting the development of intellectual capital.

In our opinion, the depreciation of human capital in our country should be viewed from the perspective of the weakening of its investments. In order to overcome this, investments should be increased in the main areas where human capital is invested, in education and improving health care. Education as a factor covers all relevant stages. In this case, it should be considered as the accumulation of knowledge and skills during the entire period of human capital formation. It is appropriate to consider education as an indicator as a qualitative component of human capital, because education affects all elements of human capital formation and creates national wealth.

At present, it is necessary to understand the state of the country, taking into account the quality of human capital, the characteristics of the education system and the level of technology use in production.

Outstanding academician of Azerbaijan A.Kh. Mirzajanzadeh writes in his book "Studies of Science" that as a factor influencing the development of human capital, it should cover all stages of education according to the principle of "lifelong education" [8]. In this regard, the economy based on the application of knowledge and technology is the main factor for performance indicators of qualitatively new transformations in building a qualitatively new society with high technological characteristics.

In all developed countries, attention is paid to the dependence of investments in higher education in the development of human resources (Figure 2).

As can be seen from the picture, of course, the higher the quality characteristics of the specialists working in the fields of scientific research and production, the higher the cultural and intellectual level of the country, and the economic growth in all areas of the economy.

Based on the analysis of the labor market of our republic, it can be concluded that the level of professionalism of personnel in this field in the country is far from meeting modern scientific and technical requirements. Because the funds allocated by the state to the higher education system in Azerbaijan are not enough. It is one of the main components that have a negative impact on the development of a competitive economy.

Figure 2. Dependence of human capital on "Higher education".

In world experience, 2 models of higher education financing are used (Figure 3, 4).

Figure 3. Model I – Financing of higher institutions

The first model - funding is provided by the state through allocation of transfers directly to the universities themselves. In addition, business structures participate in this process by using investment subsidies within the framework of joint research activities, having tax benefits, and attracting sponsorship.

Figure 4. Model II. Funding of education by entities (firms).

The second model is funding through an educational entity. Universities then receive funds from the state to pay for students' tuition [6].

In many countries, both models are used simultaneously, funding occurs in parallel - both the object and the subject of the higher education system.

At the current stage of the development of the innovation process, it is necessary to actively include the universities that have significant potential in the organization of teaching and scientific activities, conducting research in natural and technical sciences, into the innovation system.

Directions for improving the management of intellectual resources in the economy.

In the conditions of modern innovative development, increasing the efficiency of the intellectual capital of enterprises is associated with the following main directions: the development of competition and increasing the impact on the market, digital diversification and investment in the use of digital technologies, improving the quality of the state. [7].

In an innovative economy, market regulators should have the greatest impact on changes in the efficiency of intellectual capital, which are expressed in information signals about the level and quality of necessary intellectual capital, the differentiation of the payment of skilled labor, structure of demand for intellectual products and innovations. The increase in

wages, especially in the skilled labor sector, usually occurs due to the increase in the value of intellectual capital and its services.

Firms face intense competition on the demand side and need to develop personnel selection and retention systems. Searching for employees with the required qualifications, including employees with sufficient intellectual capital, is a complex task that requires significant costs.

In order to increase the efficiency of intellectual capital of enterprises, the importance of intellectual property protection institutions is increasing in competition. In the post-industrial era, economic development increasingly depends on the quality and completeness of information and the timeliness of its delivery to executives during decision-making. The entry of most countries into the global information space has created conditions for a significant increase in the transfer of information resources and technology in digital form, and acceleration of the mobility of knowledge and information.

To ensure the successful innovative development of the economy, it is necessary to control the effectiveness of intellectual capital.

In our opinion, the indicators that characterize the efficiency of the use of intellectual capital include the share of innovative, active enterprises, the share of innovative goods and services in the total volume of goods shipped, the use of intellectual property objects, the number of fundamentally new technologies created, the number of advanced production technologies used, the number of advanced production technologies created.

Thus, the labor market indirectly reflects changes in the market assessment of the personal intellectual capital of workers in certain occupations, affects investment decisions and advantages in the accumulation of this capital by organizations.

Prof. Andreev O.S. believes that the main direction of innovative development is design activity, especially service-oriented design based on the Internet of Things, when users can adapt equipment to create individual products. Development of new products of the economy, reorganization of enterprises, etc. The design sector related to the crisis is of primary importance and considers it a locomotive to get out of the crisis [9].

As the fourth industrial revolution develops, based on the application of cyber-physical production systems, the quality of intellectual capital will also change. Currently, the level of development of digitization of production in our republic is 10-12 times lower than in Estonia.

The share of digital economy is 2% of GDP [10,11].

Increasing the efficiency of gathering intellectual capital depends on the state.

In order to increase the demand for innovations, it is necessary to develop incentive mechanisms based on the strengthening of the public procurement institution. Knowledge economy sectors in our country make up 0.5% of GDP, in developed European countries it makes up 35%, and in the USA it makes up 45%.

It is appropriate to use the Chinese experience in the development of the knowledge economy in our republic. In China, government agencies allocate part of their expenses to their innovative activities, are exempted from taxes for scientific research and development expenses, and pay special attention to the development of the technology audit system [11, 12].

The prospect of using digital technologies requires a qualitatively new approach to the formation of personal intellectual capital. This task should become the most important issue for modern enterprises and innovative firms. Otherwise, there will be a depreciation of intellectual capital. Use of digital technologies and efficient use of intellectual capital

Summarizing the above, it can be noted that a significant increase in state spending on educational services should be considered. In addition, it is important to make wider use of the price difference between different specialties, to improve the quality of service and the image of higher education institutions. An increase in state spending on educational services in the higher education system can be possible with an increase in economic growth, and additional funds should be directed not only to expanding access to higher education of the population, but also to creating conditions for the formation of such education.

In international practice, the system of Activity-Based Methodologies (methodology of purposeful activity - "methodology of purposeful activity") has an active application. This methodology is used both in the financial management system of companies, in the organization of management accounting and budgeting, in financial planning, and in the management of business processes. The main advantage of the methodology is the implementation of targeted (point) management of the development of production and management processes to ensure higher efficiency [14,15]. In the field of managing the financial aspects of the company's activity, this methodology allows to manage the company's expenses in the most efficient way and to form a more accurate determination of the value of the sold products, works and services.

CONCLUSION

1. Modern theories of economic growth prove that the innovative development of economic systems depends on the involvement of intellectual resources in the continuous innovation process of various levels and content and their effective management.

2. The analysis of the innovative success of the leading countries allows us to conclude that human capital and research, as well as knowledge, technology and creative results are important factors contributing to the formation of the new economy. A knowledge-intensive economy is based on human knowledge and intellectual abilities and leads to sustainable development of the economy as a whole.

3. Azerbaijan's integration into the world economy is based on an innovative economic growth model in the development of all economic fields. In today's innovative conditions, the concept of human capital, which includes knowledge and skills, is becoming extremely relevant.

The efficiency of production activity, the success and profitability of organizations directly depends on the availability, efficient use and further development of human capital. In order for the republic to have sustainable economic growth and competitiveness, special attention should be paid to the development of education and science, which play a leading role in human capital.

4. Ensuring the sustainable development of the economy as a research object for the development of innovative development and digital economy, a new type of innovative economy should be formed on the basis of an economic system based on the integration of science and high technologies

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